

ATTITUDE OF THE HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS TOWARDS LIFE SKILLS

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Abstract

Education is most important part of any society. Mind of any person can be transform through education. Life skills also a part of any person personality. There are many life skills but in the given study investigators took ten life skills i.e. critical thinking, decision making, problem solving, Decision making, Creative thinking, Effective Communication, Interpersonal relationships, Self-awareness, Empathy, Coping with emotion and Coping with stress. To access attitude towards life skills a sample of 220 higher secondary students were taken from different schools on the basis of purposive random sampling from Deoghar district. Attitude Scale by N.S. Chauhan and Saroj Aurora, Meerut and Life skills Assessment Scale (2014) by Dr. R. Subashree and Dr A. Radhakrishnan Nair was used for data collection. The investigators result on the basis of gender and type of management shows is significant difference in life skills of higher secondary students. The result also shows that there is no significant difference towards attitude based on gender, locality of school, type of management and parental qualification. There is no significant difference towards life skills based on locality of school and parental qualification. The findings reveal that there is no significant relationship in the attitude towards Life Skills among the higher secondary students. The same kind of study can be carried out by increasing the number of variables and factors to get the narrowed results. The same study may be extended to another geographical region. So as to generalize the findings of the present study or compare with other regions. In the similar manner further study can be conducted to analyze attitude and Life Skills among all type of students at school level as well as college level or academia level.

Introduction:

Education plays a powerful role in building a good and powerful society. As a person sharpens his mind with the use of knowledge, his consciousness develops and mind becomes more logical. He also able to develops his skills. Young people are considered the major agents in their own development, which means that they have the ability to create the supportive relationships and communities they need to grow and succeed. In the present scenario, students face many types of challenges regarding their studies and life. As the present life style, skills become faint for example calculator makes calculation easy so we escape from mind calculations. Life Skills Based Education aims to help children reach their full personal potentials and to prepare them for the challenges of everyday life. Life skills based education has a long history of supporting child development and health promotion in many parts. In 1986, the Ottawa Charter for Health Promotion recognized life skills in terms of making better health choices. The main need of the study was to explore the attitude towards Life skills towards higher secondary students. It is practically impossible to teach without passing on some of the values that the teacher ascribes to. To achieve this, the aim of establishing the extent to which life skills education was being taught among students how life skills education training had equipped teacher to teach it in schools and to identify challenges teachers were facing in implementing life skills education. In addition to recommend measures to be undertaken to improve practice of morality in students. The Life Skills Education will bring long term benefits to the society. These include educational, social, health, cultural and economic benefits

Statement of the Problem:

The problem taken up by the investigator is stated as "Attitude of the Higher Secondary Students towards Life Skills".

Method of the Study:

The descriptive survey method gathers data from large number of cases at a particular time. It is interested in knowing something about the whole population. The present investigation aims to study the "Attitude of higher secondary students towards life skills" Therefore, the investigator adopted the purposive random sampling for the present study.

Sample of the Study:

A sample is a small portion of a selected for observation and analysis of the data. By the process of sampling a relatively small number of individuals, objects or events are selected or analysed in order to find out something about the entire population or universe from which it was selected. For the present study the investigator select 220 higher secondary students in Deoghar District by the method of Random Sampling.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out if there exists any significant difference between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school with respect to their attitude.
- To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of type of management with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their life skills.

- To find out if there exists any significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school with respect to their life skills.
- To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of type of management with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.
- To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.
- To find out the significant relationship between higher secondary students with respect to their attitude and life skills.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- There is no significant difference exists between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- There is no significant difference exists between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- There is no significant difference exists among sub samples of type of management with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- There is no significant difference exists among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- There is no significant difference exists between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their life skills.
- There is no significant difference exists between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their life skills.
- There is no significant difference exists among sub samples of type of management with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.
- There is no significant difference exists among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.
- There is no significant relationship between higher secondary students with respect to their attitude and life skills.

Variables of the Study:

- Attitude Scale
- Life skills

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

- Gender : Male/ Female
- Locality of School : Rural / Urban
- Type of Management : Government / Aided/ Private
- Parental Qualification : Illiterate / School Education / College Education

Tools Used In the Present Study:

- Attitude Scale by N.S. Chauhan and Saroj Aurora, Meerut.
- Life skills Assessment Scale (2014) by Dr R. Subashree and Dr A. Radhakrishnan Nair was adopted in the present study.

Description of the Tools:

Attitude Scale:

Attitude possesses a scientific status as hypothetical construction. Attitude refers to an aspect of personality inferred to account for both persistency and consistency of behaviour, towards a family of related situations or objects. Attitudes are pre-dispositions to action exhibit variation between individuals and cultures but are different both from instructs and habits. Possessing beliefs attitudes by nature are evaluative or effective.

Scoring Procedure of Attitude Scale:

To be used by the tester afterwards. The tester is to fill the schedule of the sheet himself. He must tick himself the item ticked by the testee and fill up. Attitude wise total score of the ticked items be filled in the table space, provided on the facing page of the scoring sheet.

Life Skills:

Life Skills are defined as “the abilities for positive behaviour that enable and empower individuals to meet the challenges of everyday life.” Life Skills promote interpersonal skills that help people to empathize with others, communicate effectively, make decisions, think critically and creatively to solve problems, cope with stress and help build healthy relationships to live life in a healthy and productive manner.

Scoring Procedure of Life Skills:

The Life skills scale comprises of 100 items which has both negative and positive statements with a 5-point Likert scale for the students to check the appropriate response which can be most descriptive of him/her viz., Always true of me, Very true of me, Sometimes true of me, Occasionally true of me, Not all true of Me. The statements carried the weightage of 5,4,3,2,1 The maximum possible score of of Life skills is given 50 to 500.

Statistical Techniques Used In the Study:

The data was analyzed using SPSS 20. An objective wise analysis of data was done by the researcher.

- Differential Analysis - ‘t’ test and ‘F’ test and Regression Analysis - ‘r’.

Differential Analysis for Attitude Scores of Higher Secondary Students:

Table 1: ‘t’ - Values Between Male and Female Higher Secondary Students With Respect in their Attitude

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Male	115	127.54	16.095	0.471	NS
Female	105	128.55	15.452		

It is evident from Table 1, the calculated 't' value is 0.471, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.

Table 2: 't' - Values Between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Students With Respect in their Attitude

Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	138	128.38	14.809	0.435	NS
Urban	82	127.42	17.330		

It is evident from table 2, the calculated 't' value is 0.435, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.

Table 3: 'F' Values for Attitude Scores-Higher Secondary Students - Based on Type of Management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	399.113	199.556	2	0.802	NS
Within Groups	54024.724	248.962	217		
Total	54423.836		219		

Table 3, the calculated 'F' value is 0.802, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.

Table 4: 'F' Values for Attitude Scores-Higher Secondary Students - Based on Parental Qualification

Parental Qualification	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	335.666	167.833	2	0.673	NS
Within Groups	54088.170	249.254	217		
Total	54423.836		219		

Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 0.673, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.

Differential Analysis for Life Skills Scores of Higher Secondary Students:

Table 5: 't' - Values Between Male and Female Higher Secondary Students with Respect in their Life Skills

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	115	384.14	29.582	2.982	S
Female	105	372.41	28.645		

It is evident from Table 5, the calculated 't' value is 2.982, which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was rejected and research hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that there is significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their life skills.

Table 6: 't' - Values Between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Students With Respect in their Life Skills

Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	138	379.21	30.488	0.427	NS
Urban	82	377.43	28.359		

It is evident from Table 6, the calculated 't' value is 0.427, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their life skills.

Table 7: 'F' Values for Attitude Scores-Higher Secondary Students - Based on Type of Management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	6767.886	3383.943	2	3.950	S
Within Groups	185884.564	856.611	217		
Total	192652.450		219		

Table 4.7, the calculated 'F' value is 3.950, which is not significant at 0.05 accepted. It is inferred that there is significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.

Table 8: 'F' Values for Life Skills Scores-Higher Secondary Students - Based on Parental Qualification

Parental Qualification	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	1385.675	692.837	2	0.786	NS
Within Groups	191266.775	881.414	217		
Total	192652.450		219		

Table 8, the calculated 'F' value is 0.786, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.

Correlation Analysis:

Table 9: Correlation Coefficient Values For Attitude and Life Skills of Higher Secondary Students

Variables	N	'r' Value
Attitude and life skills	220	0.029 NS

Level of Sig - 0.05

S - Significant

NS - Not Significant

In the present study attitude and life skills of the higher secondary students. Table 9 shows that the 'r' values for attitude and life skills of higher secondary students 'r' value 0.029 is lesser than the table value of 0.997 to be significant at 0.05 level.

Therefore, the research hypothesis accepted null hypothesis is rejected. Further it is found that there is no significant relationship between attitude and life skills of higher secondary students.

Findings of the Study:

- It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- It is inferred that there is significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their life skills.
- It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their life skills.
- It is inferred that there is significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their life skills of higher secondary students.
- It is found that there is no significant relationship between attitude and life skills of higher secondary students.

Conclusion:

On the other hand there are no differences between attitude and life skills on the basis of locality of school and parental qualification. Life skill and its consequences could be either positive or negative. Proper life skill education at this phase can serve as a remedy for students. Life skill education is a need of society and every education system should impart life skill education as a part of its curriculum as it is capable of producing positive health behaviour, positive interpersonal relationships and the well-being of individuals. Hence, the teachers and the stakeholders of higher secondary schools should try to organize more co-curricular activities to expose the hidden talents of the students and raise their attitude level and acquire life skills. The schools must make the children aware of the need and significance of life skills for the success of their future. They should also make aware of their strengths and weakness.

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